

**24th European Colloquium on Theoretical and Quantitative Geography, Tallinn
(Estonia), September 10-14, 2025**

Title: Maximising sunflower crop yield, pollinator diversity and carbon sequestration in the Vojvodina region (Serbia) through spatial optimisation of Nature-based Solutions

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Keywords: Evolutionary algorithms, Ecosystem services, Multi-objective optimisation, Land use, Climate adaptation and mitigation

Abstract:

Agriculture is under increasing pressure from climate change, as farmers are seeing their crop yields drop and become more unpredictable due to increasingly frequent droughts, loss of soil carbon and the decimation of insect pollinators. Nature-based Solutions (NbS), like embedding flower strips along field edges, protecting and expanding semi-natural grasslands, and planting new forests, provide useful ecosystem services that mitigate these pressures, enhance biodiversity and reduce net carbon emission. NbS have a positive impact on nearby fields and provide a pathway to more sustainable and climate-resilient farming. Finding optimal locations for NbS however, that maximise benefits with minimal costs, is a complex spatial exercise that is complicated further by possibly conflicting priorities of the involved stakeholders, including farmers, policy makers and nature conservation groups.

The primary aim of the research is to simulate areal demands of three types of NbS: 1. crop field with flower strips, 2. semi-natural grassland and 3. forest. These NbS are to be allocated to optimal locations in the Vojvodina region (Serbia), the study area of the ongoing SONATA project in which this work is embedded. The locations of NbS are considered optimal insofar that they maximize the three ecosystem services targeted by this study: 1. sunflower crop yield, 2. carbon sequestration and 3. pollinator diversity. A secondary aim is to provide complementary perspectives on the ecosystem services realized by alternative yet equivalent solutions.

To achieve our aims, we are developing a tool for multi-objective heuristic spatial optimisation that draws on evolutionary learning algorithms. The objective criteria to be maximised with optimisation are Ecosystem Service Indicators (ESI) that assess the three above-mentioned ecosystem services. The used ESI functions will be derived empirically

from data collected during field work, that will be performed by our project partners. The field work will assess, among other things, the spatial relationship between crop yield variations, the observed local presence and abundance of pollinator species, and the interconnectivity of NbS in the vicinity of crop fields. The model space reflects the current state of the study area in terms of land use and habitat types that can be linked to the three above-mentioned NbS. The model space will be derived from EUNIS level 3 habitat type maps, that will themselves be derived from remote sensing data by our project partners, and other GIS layers like field masks and crop classification maps. The spatial variables included in the decision functions are context-sensitive indicators that are derived from the current model space using moving window or similar operators. Examples of spatial variables that can be useful for this work are ecological connectivity and relative frequencies of NbS. The values yielded by the decision functions allow the model to generate solutions and to gradually improve initially suboptimal solutions. Given the nature of the problem and the fact that the optimisation practically comes down to finding optimal quantitative values for the weights included in the decision functions, we are exploring Multi-Objective Differential Evolution (MODE; Xue et al., 2003; Babu & Jehan, 2003; Robič & Filipič, 2005) as a potentially suitable modelling framework.

The presentation will treat the methodology, expected outcomes, and possibly some experimental results, obtained with the proposed tool. We will also cover the used techniques for evaluating the performance of the model. We pose that the proposed tool and its generated outputs will provide a sound basis to launch the development of an online geo-platform with which we aim to involve stakeholders in a second phase of the SONATA project. The presented research can support policy design, inform stakeholders and engage them to find a maximally beneficial spatial configuration of NbS.

References

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